

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

ESSENTIAL CRITICISM OF "ADOLAT MANZILI" ("JUSTICE VENUE") BY ADIL YAKUBOV

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Annotation: *Adil Yakubov is a great literary representative whose contribution to the development of Uzbek literature is invaluable. The following article draws some views about the author's peculiar literary style, the novel "Adolat manzili" ("Justice Venue") and social, spiritual problems discussed in the novel, themes focused on the work.*

Key words: *Adil Yakubov, XX century, theme, novel, literary style, prose, writer, fiction, novelist, spiritual, moral, social, situation.*

It is crucial to study the history, the period and conditions, contributing factors in the success of any work that is going to be discussed, because it helps to comprehend the topic, problem, main idea focused in the literary work. Regarding these aspects several similarities between the following novels that are about to be compared are observed. Both works were written at the end of the authors' creative path and could be evaluated as the product of the writers' life and creative experience.

One of prominent representatives of Uzbek literature Adil Yakubov's novel "Adolat manzili" ("Justice Venue") is also the result of a long life experience and creative maturity. The author experimented different artistic skills in various genres and styles, working creatively in the period when it was the time of complex socio-political changes. But in all his works, the deep understanding of the essence of the nation's spirituality, high moral and aesthetic values, was always the basis of his creative artistic research. The depiction of the spiritual, moral and social interrelationship between the people and the period dominates in the novel. According to the writer's point of view, both these problems of the society should be comprehended; the conclusions achieved during the discussion should be transmitted to the reader, thus these both gain a deep aesthetic value. The author pays special attention to the description of the essence of poetic research in the socio-psychological development of human existence. The content expressed in the

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"Adolat manzili" ("Justice Venue") is interrelated with the interests and aspirations of the people.

Literary critic Naim Karimov describes the novel as follows: "The novel is a literary genre that can reflect deeply and distinctly all classes of society, the lives of people of all categories, their inner experiences, details of everyday life and life problems" [1]. Indeed, in the novel, Adil Yakubov describes the people belonging to different classes of the ruling society, their feelings, and the problems of the time. The novelist created his work at a time when the spiritual, moral and social situation in the country was complicated. Naturally, this discomfort and anxiety was reflected in his creative pattern.

Adil Yakubov's "Adolat manzili" ("Justice Venue") is watered down with concern and sympathy for the present and future of the nation. The writer rebels against the injustice of the ruling system and mourns the plight of the people in the example of the fate of his heroes. In some places characters show their discontent in the dialogues, but in some places they express their dissatisfaction with the help of internal monologues. Azmiddin Nosirov notes that in Adil Yakubov's novel "Adolat manzili" ("Justice Venue") the text consists of logically connected communicative connections [3]. This connection consists of a stream of mythopoetic thinking based on the legend of Marjantav (Marjan Mountain). Describing the protagonist's appeals to Marjantav, his warm impressions on a happy day, on sorrowful times waiting for salvation from nature, the novelist transfers the gap between grandparents and grandchildren from the soul to the being. The description of the rural way of life carries a specific purpose in the novel. The writer sprinkles rural life on the analogy of the characters (Veteran-Suyun Burgut-Mansur Mesh-Marjonoy). The logical connection between Marjantav's songs and the tragedy of Suyun Burgut fills the literary gap. In fact, this tragedy was an expression of the suffering and anxiety that befell the nation. So, the author tries to penetrate the consciousness and worldview of the nation by covering the tragedy of an individual. In the novel, through the strong and amiable old man, who spared both his life and health for the government, the aspirations of the government towards the human destiny are exposed [4]. Exposing the inferior methods and tricks of the political-legal forces in the colonial mood, their original appearance is revealed. The Veteran, who has devoted half a century of his life to government affairs, feels helpless like a child and regrets his past as he encounters dishonest, irreligious, quarrelsome, corrupt, accused officials. It seems that the scope of traditional realism changes and improves in a positive way according to the opportunities provided by objective conditions and the life experience of a

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particular writer, his way of thinking, his intellectual weight, coverage and style of expression. In the example of the heroes, the writer describes honesty, loyalty, courage, pride that exists in the nation.

The following themes are common for the novel:

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Explanation through examples:</i>
<i>friendship</i>	<i>close relationship between Lochin, Kumush and Salim, support between them</i>
<i>family ties</i>	<i>depiction of sincere relationships, family traditions and values on the example of Veteran's extended family</i>
<i>Love</i>	<i>love between Suyun Burgut and Marjonoy</i>
<i>betrayal</i>	<i>Mansur Mesh's betrayal to his neighbors</i>
<i>respect for ancestors</i>	<i>Suyun Burgut appreciates national traditions</i>
<i>father-child problems</i>	<i>a warm father-child relationship is expressed</i>
<i>loyalty</i>	<i>Marjonoy's loyalty as a wife and as a son Lochin's trust to Suyun Burgut, his father</i>
<i>honesty</i>	<i>as one of the qualities of the protagonist Suyun Burgut</i>
<i>courage</i>	<i>Suyun Burgut's superiority over the ruthless defenders of law, his desire for justice, and his steadfastness to death</i>

The principle of a new interpretation of man and his socio-spiritual and biological world is clearly reflected in the novel. In it the inextricable link between man and nature, man and society can be observed. The image of both relationships was aimed at the same goal. While the creative novel expresses the way of life of mankind, the continuity of spiritual relations has paved the way for a full understanding of the beginning and end of human life, destiny and existence. The deepening of interpretation and analysis of Adil Yakubov 's creative thinking can be noticed in the work.

In short, Adil Yakubov expresses his concern about the changes and vices in the society of the time. One of the attractive factors of the novel's success is the idea expressed by the author. Naturally, themes such as friendship, respect for

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ancestors, family, child rearing, betrayal, love, loyalty and courage take the lead in the novel "Adolat manzili" ("Justice Venue").

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